

Multinuclear complexes derived from bi-1,8-naphthyridine ligands[†]

Nabanita Sadhukhan, Sayantani Saha and Jitendra K. Bera*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, Kanpur-208 016, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : jbera@iitk.ac.in

Abstract : 2,2'-Bis(1,8-naphthyridine) (NP₂) and 2'-methyl-2,3'-bi(1,8-naphthyridine) (MeNP₂) ligands have been synthesized via Friedlander condensation. NP₂ ligand displays chelate, bridge as well as bridge-chelate binding modes with metal ions. Mononuclear [Co(NP₂)Cl₂] (1) was isolated in the reaction of CoCl₂ with NP₂. Use of diruthenium(II) [Ru₂(CH₃CN)₆(CO)₄][OTf]₂ provided a dinuclear bridged-chelate complex [Ru₂(μ-NP₂)₂(CO)₄][OTf]₂ (2). A tetra-nuclear copper(I) complex [Cu₄(NP₂)₅][ClO₄]₄ (3) was isolated with [Cu(CH₃CN)₄][ClO₄] where both bridge-chelate and bridge coordination modes of NP₂ are utilized. Treatment of 2'-methyl-2,3'-bi(1,8-naphthyridine) (MeNP₂) ligand with [Cu(CH₃CN)₄][ClO₄] provides polymeric {Cu₂(MeNP₂)₃}[ClO₄]₂ (4).

Keywords : Naphthyridine, cobalt, ruthenium, copper, coordination polymer, solid-state structure, fluorescence.

Introduction

1,8-Naphthyridine and its derivatives are proven to be a useful class of ligands for a variety of metal ions¹. The *syn* disposition of nitrogen lone pairs of the naphthyridine unit is suitable for bridging between two metal ions². Functionalization at the 2-position of the naphthyridine with donor groups (R) like pyridyl (py), thiazolyl (tz), furyl (fu), thienyl (th) etc., provide a ligand system which are most suited to hold two metal centers in close proximity³. This set of ligands allows variation of donor units at axial sites on the bimetallic compounds^{3b,3d,4}. The coordination and electronic versatility of the naphthyridine ligands have driven their applications in a wide range of reactions – C-H activation on bimetallic platforms⁵, C-C bond formation reactions⁶, bimetallic catalysis⁷, bimetallic Water-Gas-Shift reaction⁸, bifunctional water activation for nitrile hydration⁹ etc. Metal complexes containing naphthyridine functionalized N-heterocyclic carbene ligands are excellent catalysts for carbene transfer reactions^{6c,7c,9a,10}. Two naphthyridines linked by a ferrocene unit was employed to construct mixed-metal assemblies¹¹. Direct linking of two naphthyridine units offers an exciting prospect to synthesize multinuclear complexes¹². Annulation between two naphthyridine units provides structural rigidity to the ligand and hence stabi-

lizes only mononuclear complexes involving bidentate chelate binding¹³. It has been revealed from a series of 3,3'-annulated 2,2'-bi(1,8-naphthyridine) conjugates that chain length of the bridge influences relative orientation of two naphthyridine rings and controls the coordination and electronic behavior of the ligands¹⁴. In this work, we report covalently linked bi-naphthyridine conjugates 2,2'-bi(1,8-naphthyridine) (NP₂) and methyl substituted 2'-methyl-2,3'-bi(1,8-naphthyridine) (MeNP₂) ligands (Scheme 1). An array of mono, bi, tetra and poly-nuclear metal complexes using NP₂ and MeNP₂ are synthesized and their solid-state structures and spectroscopic properties are examined. The influence of methyl substitution at 2-position of one of the naphthyridine ring towards its coordination behavior to metal center is demonstrated.

Line drawings of NP₂, and MeNP₂

Materials and methods :

Solvents were dried by conventional methods and dis-

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

tilled over nitrogen. The metal salts $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was purchased from SD Fine-Chem Limited, India. $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (39% Ru) was purchased from Arora Matthey, Kolkata. $[\text{Ru}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_6(\text{CO})_4][\text{OTf}]_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4][\text{ClO}_4]$, 2-aminonicotinaldehyde and ligand NP_2 were synthesized according to the literature procedures¹⁵.

All reactions were carried out under N_2 atmosphere with the use of standard Schlenk-line techniques. Elemental analyses were carried out using a Thermoquest CE instruments model EA/110 CHNS-O elemental analyzer. Samples were powdered and dried in vacuum for a prolonged period (8–16 h) prior to elemental analyses. ESI-MS was recorded on a Waters Micromass Quattro Micro triple-quadrupole mass spectrometer. ^1H NMR was obtained on a JEOL JNM-LA 400 MHz spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Bruker Vertex 70 FTIR spectrophotometer in the ranges from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} using KBr pallets. Electronic absorptions were measured on Perkin-Elmer Lambda-20 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Emission spectral data were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer LS 50B Luminescence spectrometer. Degassed acetonitrile solvent was used for the emission measurements in the concentration range of 10^{-5} to 10^{-6} M. Cyclic voltammetric studies were performed on a BAS Epsilon electrochemical workstation in acetonitrile with 0.1 M tetra-n-butylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF_6) as the supporting electrolyte. The working electrode was a BAS Pt disk electrode, the reference electrode was Ag/AgCl and the auxiliary electrode was a Pt wire. The ferrocene/ferrocenium couple occurs at $E_{1/2} = +0.51$ (70) V versus Ag/AgCl under the same experimental conditions. The potentials are reported in volts (V); the ΔE ($E_{p,a} - E_{p,c}$) values are in millivolts (mV) at a scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} .

Details of X-ray data collection and refinements :

Single-crystal X-ray studies were performed on a CCD Bruker SMART APEX diffractometer equipped with an Oxford Instruments low-temperature attachment. Data were collected at 100(2) K using graphite-monochromated Mo-K_α radiation ($\lambda_\alpha = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The frames were indexed, integrated and scaled using the SMART and SAINT software packages¹⁶, and the data were corrected for absorption using SADABS programs¹⁷. Structures were solved and refined with SHELX suite of programs as

implemented in X-seed¹⁸, while additional crystallographic calculations were performed using PLATON¹⁹. The crystallographic figures have been generated using Diamond 3 software (50% probability thermal ellipsoids)²⁰. Hydrogen atoms were included at geometrically calculated positions in the final stages of the refinement and were refined according to the 'riding model'. All non-hydrogen atoms except C8, C9 and C12 in compound **2** were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. Anisotropic treatment of these atoms resulted in non-positive definite displacement tensors and was therefore, subjected to isotropic refinement. Pertinent crystallographic data for NP_2 and compounds **1-4** are summarized in Table 1.

Synthesis of MeNP_2 :

2-Aminonicotinaldehyde (500 mg, 4.1 mmol) was dissolved in 20 mL of dry ethanol. To this, 0.19 mL of acetyl acetone (1.95 mmol) was added. The solution was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere and treated with three drops of freshly prepared saturated methanolic KOH. After refluxing overnight, the solvent was evaporated. The column chromatography (dichloromethane/methanol, 94 : 6) afforded pure MeNP_2 . Yield : 410 mg (73%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$: C, 74.98; H, 4.44; N, 20.57. Found : C, 73.23; H, 3.91; N, 21.63; ESI-MS : m/z 273 [M+H]; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 9.16 (1H, dd, NP), 9.08 (1H, dd, NP), 8.40 (1H, s, NP), 8.32 (1H, d, NP), 8.26 (1H, dd, NP), 8.19 (1H, dd, NP), 7.76 (1H, d, NP), 7.54 (1H, dd, NP), 7.45 (1H, dd, NP), 2.93 (3H, s, CH_3); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{NP})$ 1698(s), 1555(s), 1439(w), 1131(w), 940(w), 853(s), 803(s), 774(s).

Synthesis of **1** :

NP_2 (30 mg, 0.12 mmol) was added to a 15 mL methanolic solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (25 mg, 0.10 mmol) and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. The resulting blue solution was concentrated and slowly layered with ether. X-Ray-quality crystals of **1** appeared after 3 days. Yield : 33 mg (82%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{CoCl}_2\text{C}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{H}_{10}$: C, 49.51; H, 2.6; N, 14.44. Found : C, 47.97; H, 2.81; N, 13.87; IR(KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{NP})$ 1675(m), 1605(s), 1553(s), 1492(m), 1441(m), 1382(m), 1267(m), 1209(m), 1132(m), 862(m), 770(m), 673(m); ESI-MS : m/z 387 [M+H]⁺, M = $[\text{Co}(\text{NP}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2]$.

Synthesis of **2** :

NP_2 (40 mg, 0.155 mmol) was added to 20 mL aceto-

Table 1. Crystallographic data and pertinent refinement parameters

	NP ₂	1	2.2CH ₂ Cl ₂	3	4.CH ₃ CN
Empirical formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ CoN ₄	C ₄₀ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ F ₆ N ₈ O ₁₀ Ru ₂ S ₂	C ₈₆ H ₅₈ Cl ₄ Cu ₄ N ₂₃ O ₁₆	C ₅₇ H ₄₉ Cl ₂ Cu ₂ N ₁₃ O ₉
Formula weight	258.28	388.11	1298.73	2065.51	1258.07
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Orthorhombic	Triclinic	Triclinic	Triclinic
Space group	P21/n	Pbca	P-1	P-1	P-1
<i>a</i> (Å)	6.4003(11)	14.5979(12)	13.2557(11)	16.6026(13)	11.6858(10)
<i>b</i> (Å)	16.927(3)	13.6924(12)	14.3418(12)	16.6802(13)	14.0148(12)
<i>c</i> (Å)	10.927(2)	15.1711(13)	14.9965(12)	18.7460(15)	17.9459(16)
α (deg)	90	90	108.4560(10)	115.7510(10)	79.463(2)
β (deg)	95.183(4)	90	97.9860(10)	94.4120(10)	72.769(2)
γ (deg)	90	90	115.9990(10)	105.0040(10)	85.972(2)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1178.9(4)	3032.4(4)	2298.1(3)	4408.1(6)	2759.4(4)
<i>Z</i>	4	8	2	2	2
ρ_{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.455	1.700	1.877	1.556	1.514
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.091	1.487	1.072	1.154	0.939
<i>F</i> (000)	536	1560	1284	2094	1292
Reflections collected	7680	18917	20317	28951	18315
Independent	2909	3733	10789	20724	13018
Observed [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	1555	3027	8299	13793	8265
No. of variables	181	208	644	1197	754
GOF	1.015	1.062	1.050	1.093	1.047
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.0575	0.0496	0.0331	0.0295	0.0353
Final <i>R</i> indices	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0769,	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0430,	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0443,	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0684,	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0664,
[<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)] ^a	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1465	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.0927	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1031	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1730	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1498
<i>R</i> indices (all data) ^a	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.1441,	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0614,	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0642,	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.1043,	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.1131,
	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1734	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1040	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1224	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.2070	w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1954

^a*R*₁ = $\Sigma||F_o| - |F_c||/\Sigma|F_o|$ with $F_o^2 > 2\sigma(F_o^2)$. w*R*₂ = $[\Sigma w(|F_o^2| - |F_c^2|)^2/\Sigma|F_o^2|^2]^{1/2}$.

nitrile solution of [Ru₂(CH₃CN)₆(CO)₄][OTf]₂ (60 mg, 0.07 mmol) and the resulting brown solution was stirred for 8 h at room temperature. The solution was concentrated and 15 mL of diethyl ether was added with stirring to induce precipitation. The brown solid residue was washed with diethyl ether (3 × 10 mL) and dried in a vacuum to afford **2**. X-Ray-quality crystals were grown by diffusion of diethyl ether onto an acetonitrile solution inside an 8 mm o.d. vacuum-sealed glass tube. Yield : 67 mg (85%). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₈H₂₀F₆N₈O₁₀Ru₂S₂ : C, 40.43; H, 1.79; N, 9.93. Found : C, 41.21; H, 2.03; N, 9.67; ESI-MS : *m/z* 980 [M-(OTf)]⁺, M = [Ru₂(NP₂)₂(CO)₄][OTf]₂; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , ppm) : 9.59 (2H, dd), 9.15 (2H, d), 8.99 (4H, d), 8.89 (2H, d), 8.87 (1H, s), 8.86 (1H, d), 8.66 (2H, dd), 8.635 (2H, dd), 8.14 (2H, d), 7.48 (2H, dd); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν (CO) 2038(s), 2000(s), 1967(s), 1945(s); ν (NP) 1605(m),

1547(w), 1439(w), 1523(m), 1502(m), 1031(s), 917(s), 869(m), 852(m), 634(s), 563(m), 516(m); ν (OTf) 1262(s), 1155(s).

Synthesis of **3** :

The reaction of [Cu(CH₃CN)₄][ClO₄] (60 mg, 0.18 mmol) and NP₂ (57 mg, 0.22 mmol) was carried out following a procedure similar to that described for the synthesis of **2**. Yield : 54 mg (60%). X-Ray-quality crystals were grown by diffusion of diethyl ether onto an acetonitrile solution of the **3** inside an 8 mm o.d. vacuum-sealed glass tube. Anal. Calcd. for C₈₀H₅₀Cl₄Cu₄N₂₀O₄ : C, 54.86; H, 2.88; N, 15.99. Found : C, 54.21; H, 2.93; N, 15.37; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν (ClO₄) 1090(vs); ν (NP) 1602(m), 1547(w), 1499(m), 1377(m), 1298(w), 845(m), 804(m), 784(w), 622(m); ESI-MS : *m/z* 321 [Cu₂(NP₂)₂]²⁺ (*z* = 2).

Synthesis of 4 :

The reaction of MeNP₂ (60 mg, 0.22 mmol) and [Cu(CH₃CN)₄][ClO₄] (60 mg, 0.18 mmol) was carried out following a procedure similar to that described for the synthesis of **2**. Yield : 113 mg (63%). X-Ray-quality crystals were grown by diffusion of petroleum ether onto a dichloromethane solution of the **4** inside an 8 mm o.d. vacuum-sealed glass tube. Anal. Calcd. for C₅₁H₃₆Cl₂Cu₂N₁₂O₈ : C, 53.6; H, 3.17; N, 14.71. Found : C, 54.23; H, 3.49; N, 14.09; ESI-MS : *m/z* 1043 [Cu₂(MeNP₂)₃ + ClO₄]⁺, 771 [Cu₂(MeNP₂)₂ + ClO₄]⁺; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν(ClO₄) 1088(vs); ν(NP) 1601(m), 1554(w), 1498(w), 1447(w), 919(w), 855(w), 804(m), 787(w), 621(w).

Results and discussion

Friedlander condensation of 2,3-butanedione with two equivalents of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde in methanolic potassium hydroxide provided NP₂. Molecular structure of NP₂ is confirmed by X-ray crystallography (Fig. 1). The solid-state geometry reveals an anti disposition of two NP rings. The reaction of NP₂ with CoCl₂·6H₂O provided mononuclear [Co(NP₂)Cl₂] (**1**). Molecular structure of **1**

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of NP₂ with selective atom labeling. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg): N1-C1 1.307(3), N3-C9 1.318(3), C9-C8 1.491(3), N2-C8-C9-N3 179.3(2).

reveals one NP₂ ligand and two *cis* chlorine atoms bound to the Co. The N1-Co1-N3 and Cl1-Co1-Cl2 chelate angles are 79.06(9)° and 116.27(3)° respectively. The Cl-Co-N angles lie between the ranges from 110.92(7)° to 116.89(7)° illustrating a distorted tetrahedral geometry around the metal. The ESI-MS spectrum of **1** exhibits a signal at *m/z* 387 corresponding to [M+H]⁺ where M = [Co(NP₂)Cl₂].

Reaction of NP₂ with metal-metal bonded diruthenium(II) precursor [Ru₂(CH₃CN)₆(CO)₄][OTf]₂ in

acetonitrile provided a dinuclear bridged-chelate compound [Ru₂(μ-NP₂)₂(CO)₄][OTf]₂ (**2**). The solid-state structure of **2** is determined by X-ray crystallography and the dicationic unit of **2** is represented in Fig. 3. The molecular structure of **2** consists of a diruthenium(II) unit spanned by two *cis* NP₂ ligands arranged in a *cis* configuration. Each NP₂ ligand coordinates diruthenium(II) such that the N-C-N unit of one naphthyridine fragment bridges two ruthenium centers whereas N1' atom from another NP unit occupies an axial site of the diruthenium unit. The Ru-Ru bond distance is 2.6808(4) Å. The Ru-N distances are in the range from 2.130(3) to 2.204(3) Å. Each ruthenium ion is additionally bonded to two *cis* CO ligands. The N₁-Ru-N₁' *syn*-chelate angles are 75.74(11)° and 75.97(11)°. The ESI-MS signal at *m/z* 980 is attributed to the [M-(OTf)]⁺ ion on the basis of the mass and isotopic distribution pattern where M = [Ru₂(NP₂)₂(CO)₄][OTf]₂.

Fig. 2. Molecular structure of **1** with selective atom labeling. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) : Co1-N1 2.046(2), Co1-N3 2.059(2), Co1-Cl2 2.2291(8), N1-Co1-N3 79.06(9), Cl1-Co1-Cl2 116.27(3).

Fig. 3. Molecular structure of **2** with selective atom labeling. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) : Ru1-N3 2.145(3), Ru2-N6 2.184(3), Ru1-N8 2.175(3), Ru2-Ru1 2.6808(4), N3-Ru1-N2 75.74(11), N6-Ru2-N7 75.97(11).

Compound **2** is characterized by ^1H NMR spectra in methanol- d_4 . All protons except H7 (see, Scheme 1) experience coordination-induced downfield chemical shifts due to electronic depletion resulting from metal complexation with respect to the free ligand. A 0.4 ppm upfield chemical shift is attributed to the positioning of the H7 hydrogen in the shielding zone of naphthyridine ring from the second ligand.

Electrochemical studies of NP_2 and compound **2** were performed in propylene carbonate. Cyclic voltammogram of compound **2** exhibits an irreversible metal-based oxidation at $E_{p,a} = 1.17$ V. Four ligand-centered reversible reduction couples are located at $E_{1/2}$ (1) = -0.49 (70), $E_{1/2}$ (2) = -0.60 (80), $E_{1/2}$ (3) = -1.032 (84), and $E_{1/2}$ (4) = -1.22 (95) V (Fig. 4). The free NP_2 exhibits two irreversible $1e^-$ reductions at potential $E_{p,c} = -1.54$ and -2.13 respectively. Two NP_2 ligands bound to diruthenium(II) core result in four $1e^-$ reversible reduc-

Fig. 4. (a) Cyclic voltammogram and (b) differential pulse voltammogram for **2** in 0.1 M TBAPF₆/propylene carbonate at a scan rate of 100 mV/s.

tions indicating electron delocalization in the mixed-valent intermediates. The separation between first two reduction peaks is 120 mV corresponding to the comproportionation constant $K_c(a) = 1.07 \times 10^2$. The separation between the third and fourth reversible reduction potential is 200 mV, larger than the difference between the first and second reduction processes. The corresponding $K_c(b)$ is 2.40×10^3 . Both equilibrium constants indicate Class II weakly coupled systems in Robin-Day classification⁹.

Reaction of NP_2 with $[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4][\text{ClO}_4]$ in acetonitrile afforded a tetranuclear $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{NP}_2)_5][\text{ClO}_4]_4$ (**3**) exclusively. The cationic unit of **3** is presented in Fig. 5.

The molecule has a crystallographically imposed C_2 symmetry and half of the molecule is observed in the asymmetric unit. The structure of **3** consists of a pair of dimeric $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NP}_2)_2]$ fragments linked by single NP_2 ligand. In each $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NP}_2)_2]$ dimer, two Cu atoms are bridged by two NP_2 ligands in *trans* fashion using bridged-chelate binding mode. Two copper atoms possess different coordination geometries in each dimer. The tetradentate coordination imposes tetrahedral geometry to Cu1 and Cu2 adapts a T-shape geometry. The Cu...Cu separation distances are 2.7069(7) Å and 2.7252(8) Å. The ESI-MS of **3** exhibits signal at m/z 321 ($z = 2$) attributed to $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NP}_2)_2]^{2+}$. Poor solubility in common organic solvents hindered NMR and cyclic voltammetric measurements.

Friedlander condensation reaction between acetylacetone and 2-aminonicotinaldehyde afforded 2-methyl-(β -1,8-naphthyridyl)-1,8-naphthyridine (MeNP_2) ligand. Reaction of MeNP_2 with $[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4][\text{ClO}_4]$ resulted in poly-nuclear assembly $\{[\text{Cu}_2(\text{MeNP}_2)_3][\text{ClO}_4]_2\}_\alpha$ (**4**). The molecular structure of the repeating unit $\{[\text{Cu}_2(\text{MeNP}_2)_3]^{2+}\}_\alpha$ is presented in Fig. 6. Molecular structure of **4** consists of a binuclear metallamacrocycle of $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{MeNP}_2)_2]$ interlinked by an additional MeNP_2 ligand. Each copper atom is coordinated to distal nitrogen atoms from three independent MeNP_2 's, providing a trigonal planar geometry to the metal. The Cu-N distances are in the range 1.952(4) to 2.045(4) Å. The N-Cu-N angles vary in the range from 100.23(15)° to 131.64(16)°. ESI-MS study reveals that a signal at m/z 1043 corresponds to $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{MeNP}_2)_3 + \text{ClO}_4]^+$ fragment on the basis of the mass and isotopic distribution pattern.

The electronic absorption and luminescence spectra of ligands NP_2 , MeNP_2 and compounds **1-4** were determined in acetonitrile and the results are collected in Table 2. Both ligands show $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions although NP_2 displays absorptions in higher wavelength (~ 25 nm) than MeNP_2 due to ring planarity. The presence of methyl group in MeNP_2 does not allow a planar arrangement for naphthyridine rings. The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions are red-shifted upon complexation with metal ions as reflected in the absorption spectra of compounds **1** to **4**. Compound **2** exhibits multiple absorptions. The electron configuration of a paddlewheel $[\text{Ru}_2]^{2+}$ core is $\sigma^2\pi^4\delta^2\delta^*2\delta^*4$ corre-

Fig. 5. Molecular structure of **3** with selective atom labeling. Displacement ellipsoids are set at 50% probability and hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. The dicationic $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{NP}_2)_2]$ unit is presented in inset. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) : Cu1-Cu2 2.7069(7), Cu1-N9 2.029(3), Cu1-N9 2.032(3), Cu2-N6 2.128(3), N7-Cu2-N6 79.35(13), N9-Cu1-N3 130.99 (13).

Fig. 6. Molecular structure of **4** with selective atom labeling. Displacement ellipsoids are set at 50% probability, and hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) : Cu1-N1 1.978(4), Cu2-N8 1.952(4), Cu1-N3 1.978(4), N1-Cu1-N3 131.64(16), N8-Cu2-N9 130.75 (16).

Table 2. Electronic absorption and emission spectral data for NP_2 , MeNP_2 and compounds **1-4** in acetonitrile solvent at room temperature

Compds.	Absorption spectra λ_{max} , nm (log ϵ)	Emission spectra	
		Excitation λ_{max} (nm)	Emission λ_{max} (nm)
NP_2	341 (4.17), 256 (4.12), 242 (4.28), 208 (4.67)	365	408
MeNP_2	317 (4.57), 241 (sh), 211 (4.8)	368	471
1	347 (4.30), 258 (4.23), 208 (4.8)	314	406
2	524 (3.39), 372 (5.02), 356 (4.99), 288 (4.93), 248 (5.1)	325	404
3	452 (3.29), 339 (5.07), 277 (sh), 287 (sh), 242 (5.36), 201 (5.46)	341	413
4	321 (4.96), 239 (5.31), 204 (5.44)	373	465

sponding to a Ru-Ru single bond. The absorption around 372 nm is assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \sigma^*$. The lowest energy transition at 524 nm is described as MLCT, likely to be from π^* (Ru_2) to π^* (NP_2). The long wavelength absorption at 452 nm for compound **3** is assigned to charge transfer from $[\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} \dots \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}]$ core to NP unit. The absorption spectrum of **4** resembles to that of the free ligand MeNP_2 . NP_2 and MeNP_2 shows broad emission centered at 408 and 471 nm respectively. Compounds **1**, **2** and **3** exhibit similar emission spectra ranging from 360 to 500 nm with $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 406, 404$ and 413 nm, respectively. A broad emission ranging from 410 to 600 nm with $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 465$ nm is noticed upon excitation at 373 nm for compound **4**. It is abundantly clear that emission characteristics in these compounds are primarily ligand centered.

Summary

Directly linked 2,2' and 2,3'-bi-naphthyridine conjugates are synthesized. NP_2 ligand displays versatile coordination modes owing to the rotational flexibility along $\text{C}_2\text{-C}_2'$ bond. Reaction of CoCl_2 with NP_2 gives mononuclear chelate complex $[\text{Co}(\text{NP}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$ (**1**). Binuclear bridge-chelate mode is utilized to stabilize $[\text{Ru}^{\text{I}}\text{-Ru}^{\text{I}}]$ platform in $[\text{Ru}_2(\text{NP}_2)_2(\text{CO})_4][\text{OTf}]_2$ (**2**). A tetranuclear compound $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{NP}_2)_4][\text{ClO}_4]_4$ (**3**) is isolated which consists of two $\{\text{Cu}_2(\text{NP}_2)_2\}$ units linked by a NP_2 ligand. Incorporation of a methyl unit at 2-position in MeNP_2 afforded a polymeric $\{[\text{Cu}_2(\text{MeNP}_2)_2][\text{ClO}_4]_2\}_\alpha$ (**4**).

Supplementary data

CCDC 972319-972323 contain supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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